

Infrastructures in cooperation

CENAKVA is participating in the consortia of partners:

ESFRI European Partnerships

Fakulta rybnářství
a ochrany vod
Faculty of Fisheries
and Protection
of Waters

Jihočeská univerzita
v Českých Budějovicích
University of South Bohemia
in České Budějovice

South Bohemian Research Center
of Aquaculture and Biodiversity
of Hydrocenoses

MINISTRY OF EDUCATION,
YOUTH AND SPORTS

LARGE RESEARCH
INFRASTRUCTURES

Open access to the research infrastructure
is supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports
of the Czech Republic (LM2023038).

Faculty of Fisheries
and Protection of Waters
University of South Bohemia
in České Budějovice
Czech Republic

CENAKVA

South Bohemian
Research Center
of Aquaculture
and Biodiversity
of Hydrocenoses

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Large Research Infrastructure

CENAKVA

South Bohemian
Research Center
of Aquaculture
and Biodiversity
of Hydrocenoses

Services of CENAKVA LRI

CENAKVA's research infrastructure aims to improve our knowledge of freshwater ecosystems and their significance for sustainable production, conservation of biodiversity, protection of the aquatic environment, and ensuring the security of water resources essential for human life and activity.

**The call for projects
is open continuously!
Apply for Open Access;
it's easy!**

Research programmes

1
Reproductive and genetic procedures for fish biodiversity conservation and aquaculture

2
„New“ pollutants in the environment and their effect on freshwater ecosystems

3
Sustainable aquaculture with a responsible water and nutrient management

4
Freshwater ecosystems in the era of global change

Open Access Process

Project proposal preparation

Proposal sent to call manager

Proposal evaluated by head of the lab

Proposal evaluated by the board

Project implementation

Social relevance

RESEARCH

4 focused research programs

EDUCATION

Bc., MSc., Ph.D., supervision, public lectures, summer schools

LIFELONG LEARNING

ecological education for kindergartens, fish processing and cooking courses

CONSULTANCY

ministries, NGO, police, municipal authorities, companies

COMMERCIAL SERVICES

fish selective breeding, technologies for sustainable aquaculture, management of wastewater and drinking water, environmental monitoring

OPEN DATA

OPEN ACCESS

14 WORKPLACES

CENAKVA LRI follows the principle of providing open access infrastructure for experimental activities. Open access allows experimentation and free use of the expertise. To apply for access, the applicant prepares a proposal which is evaluated based on research quality, technical competence, and infrastructure availability. If the proposal is successful, the infrastructure staff will provide technical and scientific assistance to carry out the experiment.